

Lecturers' Perception on the Challenges and Prospects of Implementation of Digital Education in Public Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of digital technology has spurred the integration of digital education into traditional university settings, revolutionizing how knowledge is acquired and imparted. This study examined lecturers' perceptions of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, focusing on the challenges and prospects of its adoption. The descriptive survey research design was employed. Two research questions guided the study and were answered using mean and standard deviation. The study population comprised of 542 faculty of education lecturers, drawn from the three (3) public universities of study. The study sample comprised of 130 lecturers, drawn from the University of Port Harcourt (Uniport), Rivers State University (RSU), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, all in Rivers State, using the simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a 20-item researcher-structured 4-point rating scale questionnaire titled: "Lecturers' Perception on the Implementation of Digital Education in Universities in Rivers State (LPIDEURS)". The Cronbach Alpha reliability technique was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, yielding a reliability index of .77. The findings of the study revealed that inadequate access to reliable internet connectivity, unstable power supply and a lack of digital literacy among students were key challenges inhibiting the effective implementation of Digital Education in the three universities. It was also revealed that Digital Education presents promising prospects, including enhanced student engagements and the potential for personalized learning experiences. In light of these, the study recommended among others that universities should prioritize the provision of comprehensive digital literacy training to both students and lecturers.

Keywords: Perception, Digital education, Implementation, Challenges, Prospects and Digital Infrastructure

Introduction

In recent years, the landscape of education has undergone a significant transformation due to the rapid advancement of digital technologies. This shift is particularly notable in higher education, where digital education has become an important component of learning experience. In Rivers State, Nigeria, public universities are beginning to integrate digital education into their curricula to enhance teaching and learning processes. However, the success of this integration largely

depends on the perceptions and attitudes of lecturers, who play leading roles in implementing and facilitating digital education (Oye et al, 2012).

According to Bates, (2015), digital education is a comprehensive term that encompasses all forms of teaching and learning mediated by digital technologies. In the same vein, Siemens, (2004) defined it as a learning theory for the digital age that emphasizes the role of social and cultural context in how individuals create knowledge and learn. Digital education, also known as digital learning or e-learning, refers to the use of digital technologies, tools, and resources to facilitate and enhance the process of teaching and learning. Digital education encompasses a wide range of tools and methodologies, including online courses, virtual classrooms, digital textbooks, and various educational software. It offers numerous advantages, such as increased accessibility to educational resources, flexibility in learning, and the ability to cater to diverse learning styles (Anderson, 2008). For public universities in Rivers State, adopting digital education could mean improved educational outcomes and greater inclusivity, particularly for students who face geographical or financial barriers to traditional education (Adeoye et al, 2020).

Over the years, there has been a growing emphasis on harnessing the potential of digital education within the Nigerian higher education context. According to Afolabi and Adelokun (2022), the adoption of digital learning tools has the potential to enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes. Similarly, the work of Okebukola (2021), highlighted the imperatives of addressing challenges such as access to reliable internet connectivity and digital literacy to ensure the effective implementation of digital education.

The integration of digital education into conventional university education system has been catalyzed by the rapid advancement of digital technology. This transformational phenomenon has redefined the dynamics of knowledge dissemination and acquisition, ushering in an era of innovative pedagogical approaches. As the global educational landscape continues to evolve, the implementation of digital education has emerged as a pivotal focal point, reshaping traditional paradigms of teaching and learning. Ajadi et al, (2008) and Olaniyi, (2006), elaborated on the prevailing forms of digital education commonly adopted in Nigerian educational institutions. This involves delivering lecturers' instructional materials through CD-ROMs, allowing students to access and engage with the content at their convenience. It is however, common nowadays for lecturers to share lecture materials on Facebook, Whatsapp platforms, Youtube, etc. While some institutions have ventured into using Intranet systems for similar purposes, the upkeep of these systems is hindered by challenges such as unreliable electricity supply and the high operational costs of generators. Using the current state of affairs in Nigeria, many students opt to access the internet through their smart phones and cyber cafés due to limited access elsewhere.

Despite these potential benefits, the implementation of digital education in public universities face several challenges. These include inadequate infrastructure, limited access to reliable internet, and insufficient training for lecturers (Oye et al., 2012). In spite of these challenges confronting the integration of digital education in Nigerian education, notable institutions like the University of Ibadan, Obafemi Awolowo University, University of Benin, University of Abuja, University of Lagos, and the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) have taken steps to acquire and

implement digital education facilities. However, the number of such institutions remains relatively low in comparison to global standards and the potential contributions of digital education to economic progress. This disparity can be attributed to the geographical locations of many institutions, issues related to bandwidth, and primarily the persistent obstacle of inadequate power supply. While numerous educational establishments, both public and private, have initiated the setup of ICT centers primarily for Internet connectivity, the holistic development of comprehensive digital education centers has often been overlooked (Ajadi et al, 2008). Additionally, the attitudes and readiness of lecturers to embrace digital education are critical factors that influence its successful implementation. Lecturers' perceptions can significantly impact their willingness to adopt new technologies and integrate them into their teaching practices (Ifinedo, 2017). Understanding lecturers' perceptions of digital education is essential for developing effective strategies to overcome the challenges and maximize the benefits in Rivers State universities and the nation at large.

In Rivers State, public universities serve a diverse student population, many of whom may not have had prior exposure to digital learning tools. This diversity presents both a challenge and an opportunity. On one hand, there is a need for significant investment in training and infrastructure to ensure that both lecturers and students can effectively utilize digital education. On the other hand, the successful integration of digital education can democratize access to knowledge, making higher education more inclusive and adaptable to the needs of the 21st-century learner (Ifinedo, 2017). Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the necessity of digital education. During the pandemic, many educational institutions globally had to swiftly transition to online learning platforms to continue their academic activities. This unexpected shift highlighted both the potential and the limitations of digital education in public universities in Rivers State. Lecturers were thrust into new roles, requiring them to adapt quickly to digital teaching methods, often without adequate preparation or support (Adeoye et al, 2020). This experience has likely influenced their current perceptions and attitudes towards digital education.

The focus of this study was therefore timely and relevant as it aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how lecturers perceive the implementation of digital education, considering the recent experiences and the ongoing challenges. The insights gained from this research can inform the development of tailored professional development programs, targeted towards enhancing lecturers' digital competencies and their confidence in using digital tools effectively (Oye et al, 2012). It also aimed to contribute to the broader discourse on educational reforms in Nigeria, highlighting the role of digital education in bridging the gap between traditional and modern teaching methodologies. In the global context, where digital literacy is increasingly becoming essential, the findings of this study can help inform policy decisions and drive initiatives that align with international educational standards (UNESCO, 2020). By examining lecturers' perceptions, the study sought to identify the factors that facilitate or hinder the adoption of digital education and provide insights into how these barriers can be addressed (Adeoye et al., 2020).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine lecturers' perceptions of the challenges and prospects of implementation of digital education in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study explored lecturers' perceptions of:

- i. Challenges of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State.
- ii. Prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following two research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the perception of lecturers on the challenges of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State?
- ii. What is the perception of lecturers on the prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State?

Method

The study on lecturers' perception of the implementation of digital education in universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, adopted the descriptive survey design. Two research questions guided the study. The study population comprised 542 lecturers, drawn from the three (3) public universities of study; University of Port Harcourt (Uniport), Rivers State University (RSU), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE), all in Rivers State. The study sample was made up of 130 lecturers, selected using the simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a 20-item 4-point rating scale questionnaire titled: "Lecturers' Perception on the Implementation of Digital Education in Universities in Rivers State (LPIDEURS)", designed by the researcher and was structured based on Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). The instrument was validated by three experts in Computer Science Education, Educational Technology and Educational Measurement and Test Construction. The Cronbach Alpha reliability technique was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, yielding a reliability index of .77. The administration of the instrument was carried out personally by the researcher with the help of two research assistants. Out of 130 copies of the questionnaire administered to the respondents, a total of 126 copies were successfully retrieved and were used for data analysis. Data collected regarding the research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. In order to answer the research questions, a decision rule based on mean ratings was set thus; any perception mean score less than the criterion mean was considered negative while those equal to or higher than the cluster mean score were adopted as positive.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the perception of lecturers on the challenges of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviations for perception of lecturers on the challenges of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State

N=126

S/N	Perception of lecturers on the challenges of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State	SA (%) 4	A (%) 3	D (%) 2	SD (%) 1	\bar{x}	Σ	Decision
1	I find the current infrastructure (e.g., hardware, software, internet connectivity) in my university to be a significant adequate to support digital education.	0 (0)	6 (4.8)	30 (23.8)	90 (71.4)	1.33	0.87	Negative Perception
2	I consider personnel training on digital education tools and methodologies from my university to be sufficient for effectively implementation of digital education.	0 (0)	7 (5.6)	34 (26.9)	85 (67.5)	1.38	0.93	Negative Perception
3	My university has unlimited access to the necessary technology (e.g., laptops, and reliable internet) for participating in digital education.	10 (7.9)	15 (11.9)	26 (20.6)	75 (59.5)	1.68	1.44	Negative Perception
4	I feel confident in integrating digital education into my teaching practices.	0 (0)	0 (0)	61 (48.4)	65 (51.6)	1.48	0.98	Negative Perception
5	I admit that there are supportive administrative policies and measures in my university to promote and facilitate the use of digital education.	0 (0)	20 (15.9)	32 (25.4)	74 (58.7)	1.57	1.21	Negative Perception
6	I have steady source of power needed to access internet services	0 (0)	32 (25.4)	20 (15.9)	74 (58.7)	1.67	1.36	Negative Perception
7	I have the needed ICT training for Digital Education implementation in my university	8 (6.3)	11 (8.7)	38 (30.2)	69 (54.8)	1.67	1.37	Negative Perception
8	I can afford regular data subscription for Digital Education implementation in my university	50 (39.7)	22 (29.4)	37 (17.5)	17 (13.5)	2.95	1.80	Positive Perception
9	I can conveniently use online tools (Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Team, Skype, etc) needed for Digital Education implementation	25 (19.8)	48 (38.1)	40 (31.7)	13 (10.3)	2.67	1.98	Positive Perception

10	I support my university to implement digital (online) education instead of the normal classroom in-person interactions	38 (30.2)	61 (48.4)	18 (14.3)	9 (7.1)	3.01	1.64	Positive Perception
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation						1.94	1.36	

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree
Decision Value: Negative Perception = 0.00-2.49, Positive Perception = 2.50-4.00

The results from Table 1 revealed that lecturers in Rivers State universities have predominantly negative perceptions about the implementation of digital education. Items 1 to 7, with mean scores between 1.33 and 1.67, highlight significant challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient training on digital education tools, limited access to necessary technology for students, lack of confidence in integrating digital education into teaching practices, absence of supportive administrative policies, unsteady power supply, and lack of adequate ICT training. These findings are consistent with previous studies by Oye et al. (2012), Ifinedo (2017), Adeoye et al. (2020), and UNESCO (2020), which have all identified similar barriers to effective e-learning implementation in Nigerian universities.

Despite the predominantly negative perceptions, items 8, 9, and 10 showed some optimism among a minority of lecturers, with mean scores of 2.95, 2.67, and 3.01 respectively. This group believes they can afford regular data subscriptions, are comfortable using online tools like Zoom and Google Meet, and are willing to support the transition from traditional classroom interactions to digital education. This positive outlook suggests that while challenges are significant, there is also a recognition of the potential benefits of digital education.

Research question 2: What is the perception of lecturers on the prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard of Lecturers’ perception on the prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State.

N=126

S/N	Lecturers’ perception on the prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State.	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Σ	Decision
		4	3	2	1			

11	Implementation of Digital Education will enable me teach at my pace	96 (76.2)	22 (17.5)	3 (2.4)	5 (3.9)	3.66	3.20	Positive Perception
12	Digital Education will eradicate digital illiteracy in my students	96 (76.2)	30 (23.8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.76	3.25	Positive Perception
13	Digital Education will avail me the opportunity to attend my classes from any preferred location	65 (51.6)	61 (48.4)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.52	3.02	Positive Perception
14	Digital Education will make me more knowledgeable in the use of computer and other related online learning tools	80 (63.5)	26 (20.6)	20 (15.9)	0 (0)	3.48	3.03	Positive Perception
15	Digital Education will expand access to university education	35 (27.8)	30 (23.8)	32 (25.4)	29 (23.0)	2.56	2.30	Positive Perception
16	I think that digital education has the potential to increase student engagement in my courses.	38 (30.2)	32 (25.4)	30 (23.8)	26 (20.6)	2.65	2.37	Positive Perception
17	I feel that digital education provides greater flexibility and accessibility for both students and lecturers.	54 (42.9)	40 (31.7)	32 (25.4)	0 (0)	3.17	2.75	Positive Perception
18	I am optimistic that digital education will allow me to implement more innovative and interactive teaching methods.	39 (31.0)	37 (29.4)	26 (20.6)	24 (19.0)	2.72	2.43	Positive Perception
19	I believe that digital education can be a cost-effective solution for delivering quality education.	20 (15.9)	38 (30.2)	40 (31.7)	28 (22.2)	2.40	2.09	Negative Perception
20	I feel that digital education will afford me the opportunity to interact more closely with my students.	21 (16.7)	30 (23.8)	43 (34.1)	32 (25.4)	2.32	2.03	Negative Perception
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation						3.02	2.65	

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree
Decision Value: Negative Perception = 0.00-2.49, **Positive Perception** = 2.50-4.00

The results from Table 2 highlighted perceptions among respondents regarding the prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State. The positive perceptions are indicated by mean scores of 3.66, 3.76, 3.52, 3.48, 2.56, 2.65, 3.17 and 2.72 for items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17 and 18 with standard deviations ranging from 2.75 to 3.25. These scores suggest that many lecturers believe digital education will allow them to teach at their own pace, help eradicate digital illiteracy among students, provide the flexibility to attend classes from any location, enhance their knowledge of computer and online learning tools, and offer greater flexibility and accessibility for both students and lecturers. Their optimism also extended to believing that digital education will allow them to implement more innovative and interactive teaching methods, further enhancing their interaction with students. These positive aspects align with the findings of Adeoye et al (2020), who reported that digital education could enhance teaching quality and provide flexible learning environments.

Conversely, the results also indicated negative perceptions, with mean scores of 2.40, and 2.32 for items 19, and 20, accompanied by standard deviations ranging from 2.03 to 2.09. These scores fall within the decision value range of 0.00-2.50, reflecting a negative perception. The negative perceptions suggest that some lecturers doubt the ability of digital education to provide cost-effective solutions for delivering quality education, and enable closer interaction with students. These concerns are consistent with the challenges highlighted by Oye et al (2012), who noted infrastructure deficits and insufficient training as major barriers to e-learning in Nigerian universities.

Overall, the results revealed a complex picture of optimism and skepticism among lecturers regarding digital education in Rivers State universities. While there are clear positive perceptions about the flexibility, accessibility, and potential for enhanced digital literacy, there are also significant reservations about its ability to engage students, provide innovative teaching methods, and offer cost-effective education. Addressing these concerns through targeted interventions and supportive measures will be imperative for realizing the full potential of digital education in these institutions. These mixed perceptions mirror the broader findings in the literature, where both the benefits and challenges of digital education are widely recognized (Ifinedo, 2017; UNESCO, 2020).

Discussion of Findings

The results from Table 1 revealed that lecturers in Rivers State universities have predominantly negative perceptions about the implementation of digital education. Data analysis in Table 1 highlighted the challenges of implementing digital education as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient training on digital education tools, limited access to necessary technology for students, lack of confidence in integrating digital education into teaching practices, absence of supportive administrative policies, unsteady power supply, and lack of adequate ICT training. These findings are consistent with previous studies by Oye et al (2012), Ifinedo (2017), Adeoye et al (2020), and UNESCO (2020), which have all identified similar barriers to effective e-learning implementation in Nigerian universities. Oye et al (2012), emphasized that the lack of proper infrastructure and

training hampers the adoption of e-learning in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Ifinedo (2017), also noted the significant role of individual and organizational support in the effective use of digital tools for education. Adeoye et al (2020), highlighted the challenges posed by inadequate technological resources and training during the COVID-19 pandemic. UNESCO (2020), underscored the need for robust policy frameworks to support digital learning environments.

Despite the predominantly negative perceptions, items 8, 9, and 10 showed some optimism among a minority of lecturers. This group believes they can afford regular data subscriptions, are comfortable using online tools like Zoom and Google Meet, and are willing to support the transition from traditional classroom interactions to digital education. This positive outlook suggests that while challenges are significant, there is also a recognition of the potential benefits of digital education. This aligns with the findings by Anderson (2008) and Adeoye et al (2020), who argued that, despite existing challenges, digital education provides opportunities for flexible learning and improved access to educational resources.

The results from Table 2 highlighted mixed perceptions among respondents regarding the prospects of implementing digital education in universities in Rivers State. The positive perceptions indicated that many lecturers believe digital education will allow them to teach at their own pace, help eradicate digital illiteracy among students, provide the flexibility to attend classes from any location, enhance their knowledge of computer and online learning tools, and offer greater flexibility and accessibility for both students and lecturers. These positive perspectives align with the findings of Adeoye et al (2020), who reported that digital education could enhance teaching quality and provide flexible learning environments. Conversely, the results also indicated some negative perceptions, The negative perceptions suggest that some lecturers doubt the ability of digital education to provide cost-effective solutions for delivering quality education and enable closer interaction with students. These concerns are consistent with the challenges highlighted by Oye et al (2012), who noted infrastructure deficits and insufficient training as major barriers to e-learning in Nigerian universities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that lecturers in public universities in Rivers State largely have negative perceptions towards the implementation of digital education. This was because they perceived inadequate infrastructure, insufficient training, limited access to the necessary technology, and the absence of supportive administrative policies as challenges militating against the implementation of digital education in universities in Rivers State. These barriers align with the findings of previous studies, highlighting systemic issues that need urgent attention to facilitate the effective adoption of digital education. Despite these challenges, there were notable minority of lecturers who perceived the prospects of digital education positively. They believe in its potential to offer greater flexibility, improve digital literacy, and enhance the overall educational experience for both students and educators. This optimism, although less widespread, suggests that with the right interventions—such as improved infrastructure, comprehensive training programs, and supportive policies—the positive perspective of digital education can be harnessed more broadly.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed;

1. Rivers State and indeed, other public universities should prioritize improving power and internet infrastructure as well as providing comprehensive digital literacy training to both students and lecturers.
2. The universities should leverage the identified prospects by fostering a blended learning approach that combines traditional teaching methods with digital tools, thereby optimizing student engagement and learning outcomes.
3. The universities should collaborate to develop a shared repository of high-quality digital learning materials, reducing redundancy and optimizing resource utilization.
4. Universities need to develop and implement supportive administrative policies that will facilitate the integration of digital education.

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